

was highest with common carp (71.4%), and lowest with rohu (48.1%) (see table). Weight increase of common carp was 13.07 times initial weight. Weights of other species increased 4.91-6.80 times. Although the rice area was reduced

14%, there was little difference in grain yield from plots with fish (4.6 t/ha) and control plots (4.7 t/ha). The additional cost incurred in raising fingerlings (preparation of trench, fish stock, feed, labor) was \$485/ha per 100 d. (Only

10% of the cost of trench preparation is taken to calculate cost of one season). The total return from fish yield was \$751/ha per 100 d. Net return was \$266/ha per 100 d. □

Rice-based crop rotations for upland fields

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Upland crop rotations were tried 1980-81 under partially irrigated conditions at the Regional Research Station, Semiliguda, Koraput (884 m, 18°20' N, 82°30' E) in a randomized block design with 4 replications. Short-duration rice was direct sown during the wet season under rainfed conditions, followed by wheat cultivar Utkalika, gardenpea Bonneville, chickpea JG62, mustard M-27, and potato Kufri Chandramukhi in the dry season (DS). Rice varieties used were OR 165-24-12 in 1980 and Culture-I in 1981, both with 90 d duration.

The rice received 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha in 1980 and 40-9-17 kg in 1981. DS crops received the recommended package of practices. The soil was red clay loam with 5.1 pH, EC 0.168 dS/m, 0.68% organic C, 0.06% total N, 5 kg available P, and 320 kg available K/ha.

Highest yield (20.9 t/ha) was with rice - potato (see table). Rice - potato also was most efficient. Single crop rice was the most inefficient. Highest net profit was with rice - potato (see figure). □

Efficiency of crop rotations under partially irrigated conditions. Semiliguda, India, 1980-81.

Crop rotation	Yield (t/ha)		Protein ^a (t/ha)	Carbohydrate ^a (t/ha)	Energy ^a (MJ × 10 ³ /ha)
	Wet season	Dry season			
Rice - fallow	1.9	—	0.1	1.0	18.2
Rice - wheat	1.7	3.0	0.4	3.0	59.0
Rice - gardenpea (green pod)	1.7	2.5	0.2	1.1	21.4
Rice - chickpea	1.7	0.7	0.2	1.3	26.8
Rice - mustard	1.7	0.8	0.1	1.1	34.4
Rice - potato	2.0	18.9	0.4	4.7	84.3

^aProtein, carbohydrate, and energy components were calculated for edible portions only, per standards fixed by the National Institute of Nutrition (ICMR), Hyderabad, India.

Efficiency of crop rotations in terms of net profit. Semiliguda, India, 1980-81.

Zinc required for a rice - wheat sequence in alkali soils

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We evaluated Zn levels needed for a rice - wheat crop rotation in field experiments in the alkali soils of

Kumarganj. Experimental fields had pH 10.2-10.4, ESP 70-90 and EC 2-2.5 mmho/cm in 1:2 soil-water suspension. Gypsum (14% S) at 12 t or pyrite (30% S) at 4.5 t/ha had been added to improve soil conditions before the first rice crop in 1976. Plot size was 6 × 3.5 m in a randomized block design with 4 replications.

Short-duration semidwarf Pusa 2-21 was transplanted at 15 × 15 cm with 4-

Table 1. Zn requirement of transplanted rite Pusa 2-21 in alkali soils of Kumarganj, India.

Zn (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha) at foliar spray intervals of		
	1 wk	2 wk	3 wk
0	0.6	0.5	0.9
3.4	1.71.5		1.1
6.8	2.52.2		1.7
10.0	2.1	3.4	2.9
LSD (0.05)	0.3		

5 seedlings/hill. Elemental N and P were added at 120 and 22 kg/ha. Zinc sulfate (22% Zn) was applied at 0, 3.4, 6.8, and 10 kg Zn/ha as a soil drench; 1.1 kg Zn was applied as a single foliar spray at 1, 2, or 3 wk after transplanting. Medium-duration IR24 and Jaya responses to a single dose of 9 or 7.9 kg Zn/ha also were evaluated.

Without Zn and at the lower levels, rice plants developed severe Zn deficiency symptoms – leaf browning and stunted growth with eventual death of many plants. Foliar Zn spray brought a withered crop back within 3-4 d of spraying.

Zn increased grain yield tremendously

(Table 1). The responses of medium-duration varieties were even greater. At 9 kg Zn, IR24 yielded 5.3 t/ha; at 7.9 kg Zn, Jaya yielded 6.4 t/ha in 1977 and up to 6.8 t/ha in 1978, indicating a lower demand for Zn with progressive improvement in soil conditions.

Wheat was grown after rice in 6- × 4-m plots in the field treated with pyrite in a randomized block design with 4 replications. Rows were spaced 25 cm apart and sown with 125 kg seeds/ha. Fertilizer was 100-18-17 kg NPK/ha. ZnSO₄ at 0, 2.3, 4.5, 6.8, and 9.0 kg Zn/ha was applied basally at sowing. Zn deficiency caused stunted growth and poor tillering.

Table 2. Zn requirement of wheat in alkali soils of Kumarganj, India, 1976-79.

Zn (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	1976-77 (HD1982)	1977-78 (HD1553)	1918-79 (HD1553)
0	1.9	2.1	1.9
2.3	2.3	2.5	2.6
4.5	3.0	3.2	3.3
6.8	3.6	3.6	3.5
9.0	3.3	3.5	3.5
LSD (0.05)	0.4	0.3	0.3

Wheat yields increased with Zn application; 6.8 kg Zn pushed yield to 3.6 t/ha (Table 2). □

Announcements

World Food Prize to Swaminathan

M.S. Swaminathan, IRRI director general, has been named the first recipient of the General Foods World Food Prize, a new, major international award to recognize, encourage, and reward outstanding individual achievement in improving and increasing the world food supply.

Swaminathan will receive the prize 6 Oct 1987 at the Smithsonian Institution, Washington, D.C., where a colloquium on international food issues will be held in conjunction with the award ceremony.

Norman E. Borlaug, 1970 Nobel Peace Prize laureate, conceived the

World Food Prize, which is sponsored by the General Foods Fund, Inc. The prize consists of a \$200,000 cash award and a commemorative sculpture. □

IRRI - CIMMYT honored

The National Research Council and the Agency for International Development of the United States have honored IRRI and CIMMYT jointly for significant and sustained contributions in science and technology for international development over 25 yr. The awards were presented in Washington, D.C., 22 Jun 1987.

Eight nonmonetary awards recognized important efforts in using science and technology resources to help improve the lives of people in developing countries. A 2-d symposium on science and technology for development also was held on the occasion of USAID's 25th anniversary. □

New IRRI Publications

World rice statistics 1985

Appendix to the Rice economy of Asia

Training in the CGIAR system